

PROCEEDINGS

5th International Conference
Forum Wood Building Baltic
26-28 February 2024
Tallinn, Estonia

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PROCEEDINGS OF THE 5TH FORUM WOOD BUILDING BALTIC 2024

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Bioinspired living coating system for regenerative and circular architecture

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Summary

Materials exposed outdoors are prone to various deterioration processes. Architectural coatings are designed to protect surfaces against environmental and biotic degradation and/or to provide a decorative layer. Common surface treatments often include mineral oil binders and other ingredients that are known to have negative impacts on the environment. An alternative bioinspired concept for materials protection based on fungal biofilm is under development. This paper presents the first results related to the bioreceptivity of building materials and the initial steps of natural biofilm formation.

Key words: bioinspired coating system, bioreceptivity of building materials, early fungal colonizers, engineering living materials

1. Introduction

Bioreceptivity is defined as the ability of a material to be colonised by one or several groups of living organisms without necessarily undergoing any biodeterioration. An understanding of kinetic microbial colonisation on façade materials is indispensable to revealing organism-material interaction and developing a new concept for material protection. An example of such an alternative coating system based on a controlled and optimised fungal biofilm is currently under development within the frame of the ARCHI-SKIN project. In the first phase the morphological, functional, and social interactions in fungal communities naturally appearing on building materials are deeply investigated. The assessment of a variety of fungi that can thrive on exposed surfaces and understanding their interactions with various building materials is crucial to identify fungal species with a protective potential.

2. Methods

A set of 33 wood-based cladding materials were exposed to four cardinal directions and monitored in outdoor conditions on the roof of the InnoRenew CoE building, situated in the coastal town of Izola, Slovenia (45.5350, 13.6577). Multi-sensor and multi-scale measurements were performed to assess the influence of surface properties (wettability and roughness) and material structure on fungal growth, species variability, and dominance. Hyperspectral imaging (HI) as a high-throughput method was used to understand the effect of fungal growth on material properties as well as to objectively quantify the infested area. To evaluate microbial growth, the surfaces were sampled using the wet swab and plated on DG-18 agar, which prevents the growth of bacteria and limits the growth of fast-growing fungi. Pure cultures of dominant species were then isolated and identified through polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification and Sanger sequencing of specific DNA regions/genes.

3. Results and discussion

Both the material type and the climate condition at the exposure site influenced fungal colonisation. To investigate the occurrence of dominant species in more detail and in a more quantitative manner, samples where $\geq 90\%$ of the colony forming units (CFUs)

appeared to have the same morphology were identified at the 1-month timepoint. Pure cultures were obtained and selected DNA regions (internal transcribed spacers 1 and 2 including the 5.8S rDNA (ITS) and/or actin and/or β -tubulin) were sequenced to allow for identification (Fig.1). On most of the investigated materials where a dominant morphology was present, *Aureobasidium* sp. was the dominant genus, implying that *Aureobasidium* can establish dominance already during the early phases of colonisation.

Figure 1 Images of pure cultures.

4. Conclusions

Proposed techniques enabled the identification of features that promote/inhibit fungal colonization and revealed the preference of certain fungi for specific materials. Both the material type and the climate condition at the exposure site influence fungal colonization and the variability of microorganisms. The samples in close spatial proximity exhibited different fungal microbiota, demonstrating that fungal colonization across samples is not random. This study is a starting point for assays that aim to develop novel solutions for materials protection based on controlled and optimized fungal biofilm formation.

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